

Artifact for the paper “Error Invariants for Fault Localization via Abstract Interpretation”

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Abstract. In this work, we describe the installation, usage, and evaluation results of the tool, denoted `Full_AI`, introduced by the paper “Error Invariants for Fault Localization via Abstract Interpretation”. We provide step-by-step instructions on how to download, run, and compare the tool’s outputs to outputs described in the paper. The tool is a research prototype fault localizer for analyzing numerical programs in C using abstract interpretation. It uses an iterative refinement sequence of backward-forward static analyses by abstract interpretation to compute error invariants, which are designed to explain why an error program violates a particular assertion.

1 Introduction

This work summarises the evaluation results reported by the paper “Error Invariants for Fault Localization via Abstract Interpretation”. We compare three tools:

- `Full_AI` that uses an iterative refinement sequence of backward-forward static analyses to infer error invariants, which is based on the polyhedra domain from the APRON library [7], the BDDAPRON library [6], and the Z3 SMT solver [3].
- `Single_AI` that uses a single backward analysis to infer error invariants, which is based on the polyhedra domain from the APRON library [7].
- The `BugAssist` tool [8] that uses the CBMC bounded model checker [1] to generate an error trace as well as to construct the corresponding trace formula, which is then analyzed by a `MAX-SAT` solver.

2 Downloading

2.1 VM

The URL of the VM that contains the tool artifact is available from Google Drive: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1482YzEo_hJ2Bj6r9EChjz4ESm-RTXp2q?usp=sharing.

The files inside this folder are:

- Aleks.zip.001 ("md5Checksum": "065b946a2414584a6f8a5b2b12fdaf88"),
- Aleks.zip.002 ("md5Checksum": "5a86b39b0165492aa1fdc9aad4e46907"),
- Aleks.zip.003 ("md5Checksum": "2c935b701df72b39c9952cdafc95e02c"),
- Aleks.zip.004 ("md5Checksum": "427896463389c1b9e3e4643a043bc77d"),
- Aleks.zip.005 ("md5Checksum": "99789f377272ab871d787bccef57b0a3")

Once you download all files, use 7Zip to restore VM image “Aleks.ova”. The virtual machine containing the tool installed and ready to use is “user”: fase2022, “password”: fase2022.

2.2 tar.gz file

To install the tool by yourself, download the file: ErrorInvariants.tar.gz from the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/8167960>.

* Untar the given file:

```
tar -xvf ErrorInvariants.tar.gz
```

* Enter the folder that contains the tools

```
cd ErrorInvariants
```

* For step-by-step installation of the tools follow:

```
HowToInstall.txt
```

* Note that you have to install Ocaml, Apron, BDDApron, and Z3.

3 Experimental Results

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd ErrorInvariants
```

* For step-by-step execution of all test cases of the tools follow:

```
ExperimentalRESULTS.txt
```

3.1 Full_AI

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd error_inv
```

* If you want to recompile the tool, delete “Main.native” file and “_build” folder, and use the following two commands:

```
eval $(opam config env)
```

```
ocamlbuild ml_float.o Main.native -use-ocamlfind -use-menhir
```

```
-pkgs 'bddapron,apron,gmp,oUnit,zarith' -I utils -I banal -I domains
```

```
-I frontend -I main -libs boxMPQ,octD,polkaMPQ,str,zarith,bddapron
```

```
-lflags banal/ml_float.o
```

To run Full_AI on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

Note that after commands in square brackets we write:

- the reported times in seconds on our machine measured via 'real' values of the 'time' command, and

- the number of locations in the obtained program slice. Note that we do not count the locations: [1:], the assertion location, and the one after it.

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra bench/program1.c
result: [0.056 sec] [2 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
[1 :] void main(int x){ [2 :] int z := x + 1; [3 :] int y := z; [4 :] z := z+1; [5 :] assert (x > y); [6 :]	[1 :] void main(int x){ [2 :] int z := x + 1; [3 :] int y := z; Remove [4 :] [5 :] assert (x > y); [6 :]

This means that the statement in loc. [4:] is irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:] and [3:] are relevant. We do not count locations [1:] (before method definition), [5:] (the assertion definition), and [6:] (final location) in all benchmarks, since those locations are neither relevant nor irrelevant for the error. Hence, we can conclude that 2 locations in program1.c are relevant for the error (out of 3 locations, 1 loc. is irrelevant). The output log between "Abstract Syntax" of the input program and "Abstract Syntax of Program Slice" shows the results of backward and forward abstract analyses as well as the calculated Error Invariants for the input program. Their meaning is explained in the paper. Please see 'Motivating Examples' Section in the paper for detailed explanation of program1.c.

How we calculate the percentage precision "Perc%" of a given approach. There are 2 relevant locations [2:], [3:], and 1 irrelevant location [4:] obtained using Full_AI and Single_AI. The same result would have been obtained if we analyze the program using concrete semantics not abstract semantics as we did in Full_AI and Single_AI. So, we report 100% precision for Full_AI and Single_AI. On the other hand, BugAssist reports only 1 relevant location [2:], and 2 irrelevant locations [3:], [4:]. So, it correctly classifies locations [2:] and [4:], while [3:] is incorrectly classified. Therefore, its precision is $2/3 = 0.66$ (or 66%).

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra bench/program2.c
result: [0.187 sec] [5 loc]
```

<pre> Abstract Syntax: <hr/> [1:] void main(int input){ [2:] int x := 1; [3:] int y := input - 42; [4:] if (y < 0) then; [5:] x := 0; [6:] else [7:] endif [8:] assert (x > 0); [9:] <hr/> </pre>	<pre> Abstract Syntax of Program Slice: <hr/> [1:] void main(int input){ Remove [2:] [3:] int y := input - 42; [4:] if (y < 0) then; [5:] x := 0; [6:] else [7:] endif [8:] assert (x > 0); [9:] <hr/> </pre>
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This means that the statement in loc. [2:] is irrelevant for the error, while locations [3:], [4:], [5:], [6:], and [7:] are relevant. Since we do not count locations [1:], [8:], and [9:], we can conclude that 5 locations in program2.c are relevant for the error. Please see ‘Motivating Examples’ Section in the paper for detailed explanation of the output log of program2.c.

How we calculate the percentage precision “Perc%” of a given approach. There are 5 relevant locations [3:], [4:], [5:], [6:], [7:] and 1 irrelevant location [2:] obtained using `Full_AI`. This is the correct result, so we report 100% in precision for `Full_AI`. There are 4 relevant locations [4:], [5:], [6:], [7:] and 2 irrelevant locations [2:], [3:] obtained using `Single_AI`. Hence 5 locations are correctly classified and 1 location ([3:]) is incorrectly classified, so we report $5/6=0.833$ (or 83%) precision for `Single_AI`. On the other hand, `BugAssist` reports 2 relevant locations [3:], [4:], and 4 irrelevant locations [2:], [5:], [6:], [7:]. So, it correctly classifies locations [2:], [3:], [4:], while other locations are incorrectly classified. Therefore, its precision is $3/6 = 0.5$ (or 50%).

```

$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra bench/program2-a.c
result: [0.088 sec] [2 loc]

```

<pre> Abstract Syntax: <hr/> [1:] void main(int input){ [2:] int x := 1; [3:] int y := input - 42; [4:] if (y < 0) then [5:] x := 0; [6:] else [7:] endif [8:] assert (x ≤ 0); [9:] <hr/> </pre>	<pre> Abstract Syntax of Program Slice: <hr/> [1:] void main(int input){ [2:] int x := 1; [3:] int y := input - 42; Remove [4:] [8:] assert (x ≤ 0); [9:] <hr/> </pre>
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This means that statement in locations [4:], [5:], [6:], and [7:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:] and [3:] are relevant. Hence, 2 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra bench/program3.c
result: [0.453 sec] [3 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
[1:] void main(int n){	[1:] void main(int n){
[2:] int x := 6;	Remove [2:]
[3:] int y := n;	Remove [3:]
[4:] while [5:] (x < n) do	[4:] while [5:] (x < n) do
[6:] x := x + 1;	Remove [6:]
[7:] y := y + 1;	Remove [7:]
[8:]	[8:]
od	od
[9:] assert (x ≤ 10);	[9:] assert (x ≤ 10);
[10:]	[10:]

This means that statements in locations [2:], [3:], [6:], [7:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [4:], [5:], and [8:] are relevant. Hence, 3 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra bench/easy2-1.c
result: [2.401 sec] [10 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
[1:] void main() {	[1:] void main() {
[2:] int x := 7;	[2:] int x := 7;
[3:] int y := 0;	[3:] int y := 0;
[3:] int z := y;	Remove [4:]
[5:] while [6:] (x > 0) do	[5:] while [6:] (x > 0) do
[7:] if (x < 3) then	[7:] if (x < 3) then
[8:] y := y + 1;	[8:] y := y + 1;
[9:]	[9:]
else	else
[10:] z := z - 1;	Remove [10:]
[11:]	[11:]
endif	endif
[12:] x := x - 1;	[12:] x := x - 1;
[13:]	[13:]
od	od
[14:] assert (y ≤ 0);	[14:] assert (y ≤ 0);
[15:]	[15:]

This means that statements in locations [4:] and [10:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:], [3:], [5:], [6:], [7:], [8:], [9:], [11:], [12:], and [13:] are relevant. Hence, 10 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra bench/Mysore-1.c
result: [0.050 sec] [4 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
[1:]	[1:]
void main(int x){	void main(int x){
[2:] int c := 0;	[2:] int c := 0;
[3:] while [4:] (x + c ≥ 0) do	[3:] while [4:] (x + c ≥ 0) do
[5:] x := x - c;	Remove [5:]
[6:] c := c + 1;	Remove [6:]
[7:]	[7:]
od	od
[8:] assert (c > 0);	[8:] assert (c > 0);
[9:]	[9:]

This means that statements in locations [5:] and [6:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:], [3:], [4:], and [7:] are relevant. Hence, 4 locations are relevant.

The program ‘tcas1.c’ is a non-trivial example, so we have built an optimized version of the tool `Full_AI` that can efficiently handle ‘tcas1.c’. Go to folder “error_inv_tacs” using

```
cd ..
cd error_inv_tacs
compile the tool
eval $(opam config env)
ocamlbuild ml_float.o Main.native -use-ocamlfind -use-menhir
-pkgs 'bddapron,apron,gmp,oUnit,zarith' -I utils -I banal -I domains
-I frontend -I main -libs boxMPQ,octD,polkaMPQ,str,zarith,bddapron
-lflags banal/ml_float.o
and run it
$time ./Main.native -full -domain polyhedra tests/tcas1.c > tcas1full.out
result [57.78 sec] [44 loc] – the output can be seen in the file “tcas1full.out”.
The output can be seen in “tcas1full.out”. There are 44 locations that are relevant.
```

3.2 Single_AI

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd error_inv
```

To run `Single_AI` on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/program1.c
result: [0.013 sec] [2 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
[1:] void main(int <i>x</i>) {	[1:] void main(int <i>x</i>) {
[2:] int <i>z</i> := <i>x</i> + 1;	[2:] int <i>z</i> := <i>x</i> + 1;
[3:] int <i>y</i> := <i>z</i> ;	[3:] int <i>y</i> := <i>z</i> ;
[4:] <i>z</i> := <i>z</i> + 1;	Remove [4:]
[5:] assert(<i>x</i> > <i>y</i>);	[5:] assert(<i>x</i> > <i>y</i>);
[6:]	[6:]

This means that statement in locations [4:] is irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:] and [3:] are relevant. Hence, 2 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/program2.c
result: [0.187 sec] [4 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
[1:] void main(int <i>input</i>) {	[1:] void main(int <i>input</i>) {
[2:] int <i>x</i> := 1;	Remove [2:]
[3:] int <i>y</i> := <i>input</i> - 42;	Remove [3:]
[4:] if (<i>y</i> < 0) then;	[4:] if (<i>y</i> < 0) then;
[5:] <i>x</i> := 0;	[5:] <i>x</i> := 0;
[6:]	[6:]
else	else
[7:]	[7:]
endif	endif
[8:] assert(<i>x</i> > 0);	[8:] assert(<i>x</i> > 0);
[9:]	[9:]

This means that statements in locations [2:] and [3:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [4:], [5:], [6:], and [7:] are relevant. Hence, 4 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/program2-a.c
result: [0.088 sec] [6 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
<pre>[1:] void main(int input){ [2:] int x := 1; [3:] int y := input - 42; [4:] if (y < 0) then [5:] x := 0; [6:] else [7:] endif [8:] assert (x ≤ 0); [9:]</pre>	<pre>[1:] void main(int input){ [2:] int x := 1; [3:] int y := input - 42; [4:] if (y < 0) then [5:] x := 0; [6:] else [7:] endif [8:] assert (x ≤ 0); [9:]</pre>

This means that no statements are irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:], [3:], [4:], [5:], [6:], and [7:] are relevant. Hence, 6 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/program3.c
result: [0.016 sec] [3 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:	Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:
<pre>[1:] void main(int n){ [2:] int x := 6; [3:] int y := n; [4:] while [5:] (x < n) do [6:] x := x + 1; [7:] y := y + 1; [8:] od [9:] assert (x ≤ 10); [10:]</pre>	<pre>[1:] void main(int n){ Remove [2:] Remove [3:] [4:] while [5:] (x < n) do Remove [6:] Remove [7:] [8:] od [9:] assert (x ≤ 10); [10:]</pre>

This means that statements in locations [2:], [3:], [6:], [7:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [4:], [5:], and [8:] are relevant. Hence, 3 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/easy2-1.c
result: [0.011 sec] [3 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main( ) {  
[2:] int x := 7;  
[3:] int y := 0;  
[3:] int z := y;  
[5:] while [6:] (x > 0) do  
[7:]   if (x < 3) then  
[8:]     y := y + 1;  
[9:]  
       else  
[10:]    z := z - 1;  
[11:]  
       endif  
[12:] x := x - 1;  
[13:]  
       od  
[14:] assert (y ≤ 0);  
[15:]
```

Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:

```
[1:]  
void main( ) {  
Remove [2:]  
Remove [3:]  
Remove [4:]  
[5:] while [6:] (x > 0) do  
Remove [7:]  
Remove [12:]  
[13:]  
       od  
[14:] assert (y ≤ 0);  
[15:]
```

This means that statements in locations [2:], [3:], [4:], [7:], [8:], [9:], [10:], [11:], and [12:] are irrelevant for the error, while locations [5:], [6:], and [13:] are relevant. Hence, 3 locations are relevant.

```
$ time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/Mysore-1.c  
result: [0.014 sec] [6 loc]
```

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main(int x) {  
[2:] int c := 0;  
[3:] while [4:] (x + c ≥ 0) do  
[5:]   x := x - c;  
[6:]   c := c + 1;  
[7:]  
       od  
[8:] assert (c > 0);  
[9:]
```

Abstract Syntax of Program Slice:

```
[1:]  
void main(int x) {  
[2:] int c := 0;  
[3:] while [4:] (x + c ≥ 0) do  
[5:]   x := x - c;  
[6:]   c := c + 1;  
[7:]  
       od  
[8:] assert (c > 0);  
[9:]
```

This means that no statements are irrelevant for the error, while locations [2:], [3:], [4:], [5:], [6:], and [7:] are relevant. Hence, 6 locations are relevant.

```
$time ./Main.native -single -domain polyhedra bench/tcas1.c > tcas1-single.out  
result: [0.225 sec] [28 loc]
```

The output can be seen in “tcas1-single.out”. There are 28 locations that are relevant.

3.3 BugAssist

* Enter the folder that contains the tool `cd ..`

```
cd bug_assist
```

To run `BugAssist` on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands. Note that after commands in square brackets we write the reported times in seconds on our machine measured via 'real' values of the 'time' command. Moreover, `BugAssist` reports lines of code as potential bugs, while `Full_AI` locations. So, we translate the lines of code reported by `BugAssist` to locations.

```
$ time ./bugassist program1.c --ba --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [0.031] [1 loc]
```

There is 1 relevant location for the error (line 6 in `program1.c` that corresponds to location [2:] in Abstract Syntax of `Full_AI`).

```
$ time ./bugassist program2.c --ba --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [0.031] [2 loc]
```

There are 2 relevant lines for the error (lines 7 and 8 in `program2.c` that correspond to locations [3:] and [4:] in Abstract Syntax of `Full_AI`).

```
$ time ./bugassist program2-a.c --ba --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [0.031] [2 loc]
```

There are 2 relevant lines for the error (lines 8 and 9 in `program2-a.c` that correspond to locations [3:] and [4:] in Abstract Syntax of `Full_AI`).

```
$ time ./bugassist program3.c --ba --unwind 20 --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [2.954] [5 loc] BugAssist report 3 lines of code, but they correspond to
5 locations according to Full_AI syntax (e.g. there are 2 locations one before
'while' and one before 'while-guard')
```

There are 3 relevant lines for the error (lines 12, 13, and 16 in `program3.c` that correspond to locations [4:], [5:], [6:], [8:] and [9:] in Abstract Syntax of `Full_AI`).

```
$ time ./bugassist easy2-1.c --ba --unwind 8 --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [8.441] [9 loc] BugAssist report 6 lines of code, but they correspond to
9 locations according to Full_AI syntax (e.g. there are 2 locations one before
'while' and one before 'while-guard'; 2 location before and after 'then' and 'else'
branches of 'if' statements)
```

There are 6 relevant lines for the error (lines 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, and 14 in `easy2-1.c` that correspond to locations [5:], [6:], [7:], [8:], [9:], [10:], [11:], [12:], and [13:] in Abstract Syntax of `Full_AI`).

Table 1. Performance results of `Full_AI` vs. `Single_AI` vs. `BugAssist`. `Full_AI` and `Single_AI` use Polyhedra domain. All times in sec. All experiments are executed on a 64-bit 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 CPU@2.80GHz, VM LUbuntu 20.10 with 8 GB memory. All times are reported as average over five independent executions.

Bench.	LOC#	Full_AI			Single_AI			BugAssist		
		Time	Slice#	Prec%	Time	Slice#	Prec%	Time	Slice#	Prec%
program1	6	0.056	2	1	0.013	2	1	0.031	1	0.66
program2	9	0.187	5	1	0.013	4	0.83	0.031	2	0.50
program2-a	9	0.088	2	1	0.015	6	0.33	0.030	2	0.66
program3	10	0.453	5	1	0.016	4	0.71	2.954	5	0.71
easy2-1	15	2.401	10	1	0.011	4	0.53	8.441	9	0.66
Mysore-1	9	0.050	4	1	0.014	6	0.66	0.210	3	0.83
TCASv.1	118	57.78	44	1	0.225	28	0.86	0.095	1	0.62

```
$ time ./bugassist Mysore-1.c --ba --unwind 20 --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [0.210] [3 loc] BugAssist report 2 lines of code, but they correspond to
3 locations according to Full_AI syntax (e.g. there are 2 locations one before
'while' and one before 'while-guard')
```

There are 2 relevant lines for the error (lines 9 and 13 in Mysore-1.c that correspond to locations [3:], [4:], and [7:] in Abstract Syntax of `Full_AI`).

```
$ time ./bugassist tcas_v1.c --ba --maxsat ./msuncore
result: [0.095] [1 loc]
```

There are 2 relevant lines for the error (lines 143 and 159 in tcas_v1.c, but line 159 is the assertion location so we do not count it).

4 Extensibility

The tool is written in OCAML and consists of around 7K LOC. Currently, it provides only a limited support for arrays, pointers, `struct` and `union` types. The abstract operations and transfer functions of the numerical abstract domains (e.g. Polyhedra [2]) are provided by the APRON library [7]. It also uses and the BDDAPRON library [6] and calls the Z3 SMT solver [3] to compute minimal support sets. The tool is based on the tools DSPLNUM²ANALYZER [5] for analyzing `#if`-enriched C programs with numerical features and Function [9] for proving program termination.

In the folder “frontend”, the lexer and parser are implemented. In the folder “main”, the files “Main.ml”, “FullAnalysisIterator” and “SingleAnalysisIterator” describe the main program from which the tool performs analysis of the given program and the implementation of `Full_AI` and `Single_AI`. The tool can be easily extended and new options can be added.

References

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